

Building Calliope and Apollo: Engineer-Designer Reflections on Computer-Assisted Composition Systems

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Abstract

Supported by Design Science Research (DSR), Research through Design (RtD) and Technical Practice Research (TPR) methodologies, we reflect on our experience designing and building the Calliope and Apollo as Computer-Assisted Music Composition (CAC) systems. We uncover practical engineering and design learnings that contribute to the development of CAC research. With an emphasis on the Calliope system, we consider an overview of the design iterations the system has undergone, reflect on its intended creative workflow, its affordances and features. Specifically, across both systems, we report and reflect on the following engineering and design features: multi-track MIDI piano rolls, data visualizations for semantic evaluation, the management of batch-generated files, model-agnostic design, front-end local model training and technical jargon translation. We address opportunities, challenges and implications as takeaways for building effective engineering patterns and interaction design workflows of CAC systems.

1 Introduction

The development of CAC systems has been shaped by a long tradition of research and innovation, with prominent work from institutions such as IRCAM¹ (Assayag et al., 1999). The field explores music composition tools at the convergence of music theory, sound design and advanced engineering. Notable work like Flow Machines (Sony, 2013) by François Pachet and Sony CSL further highlight the possibilities of AI-driven creativity. They can be standalone (Flow Machines) or integrated in a Digital Audio Workstation (DAW) (MMM4Live (Pasquier, 2021), PIA (Hadjeres and Crestel, 2021)). Recent years have seen the proliferation of computer-assisted composition (CAC) systems that leverage advances in machine learning (ML), particularly transformer-based generative models, to support music composition workflows (Tchemeube and Pasquier, 2025). Systems such as Bach Doodle (Huang et al., 2019), MuseNet (Payne, 2019) or Calliope (Tchemeube et al., 2022), demonstrate how symbolic music generation can be integrated into interactive tools. Modern CAC systems i.e., NONOTO (Bazin and Hadjeres, 2019), Magenta Studio (Roberts et al., 2019), Calliope (Tchemeube et al., 2022), integrate frameworks such as Python-based backends and Node.js (Nodejs, 2009) for seamless web applications, addressing challenges of interfacing music AI in the browser.

Despite these advances, the development of usable CAC systems remains technically complex and often under-documented, particularly in terms of engineering workflows, design rationales, and challenges related to user interface design and integration. Few CAC research effectively report on their design and development efforts, most notably works on OpenMusic (Bresson et al., 2005), PIANOTO (Bazin, 2023), and Magenta Studio (Roberts et al., 2019). Such information is rarely articulated in sufficient detail. It is a necessary exercise to capture learnings for CAC research and

¹IRCAM stands for the Institute for Research and Coordination in Acoustics/Music.

Calliope 0.10 - Annotated (2023) *

Calliope 0.11 - Light (2024)

Calliope Mockup (UX Study) (2023)

Calliope 0.11 Mockup (2023)

Calliope 0.11 - Dark Annotated (2024) *

Calliope 0.9.5 (2022) *

Calliope 0.11 Mockup Iteration (2023)

Calliope 0.11 Wireframe (2023)

Calliope 0.11 Design Test (2023)

Calliope 0.10 Layout Iteration (2022)

Calliope 0.10 Layout Mockup Test (2022)

Figure 1: Calliope’s Annotated Portfolio – Major Design Iterations, Mockups and Sketches (2022-2024), Legend: * = Main Releases, Bold = Latest Release. (Figure can be zoomed up to 6x).

critically examine projects across literature. This gap in reporting makes it difficult for the research community to build upon prior work. Addressing it advances the state of CAC systems beyond model testing and toward robust, usable software.

Our aim is to *advance browser-based AI music tools*, looking at limitations of, and developing reusable approaches for building web-based CAC systems. To do this, we contribute *engineering and design reflections on two CAC systems* developed by the authors: Apollo² and Calliope³. These systems provides composers with advanced tools to explore unique creative music AI workflows. We also contribute an *annotated portfolio of Calliope design iterations* (Figure 1), discuss the challenges encountered, solutions implemented, unrealized design ideas and the implications for the broader field of CAC research, presented as takeaways. Overall, we seek to provide pathways for reflection, presenting findings from our research and suggesting avenues for further investigation that CAC designers and researchers can consider. By reporting on these two systems, we advance the broader goal of improving the development and effectiveness of web-based CAC tools. This work also helps support fellow researchers, developers, and practitioners engaged in the design of future web-based CAC systems by offering methodological transparency and practical insights.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 covers a short background on the CAC systems and the AI models they use. Section 3 presents the research methodologies involved. Section 4 introduces the annotated design portfolio of Calliope, documenting multiple iterations of the UI and user workflows. Section 4 and 5 discuss technical challenges and design decisions for Calliope and Apollo respectively, including cross-platform constraints, data representations, and visual design trade-offs. Section 6 synthesizes design insights and overall takeaways relevant to CAC research and development. Section 7 concludes with a call for increased documentation of design and engineering processes in the CAC community.

2 Calliope and Apollo: Systems and Models

Calliope (Tchemeube et al., 2022), a web-based application, facilitates interactive multi-track music composition by allowing users to generate new MIDI⁴ content from existing files or from scratch, supporting iterative generation and inpainting. Calliope interfaces the Multi-track Music Machine (MMM) (Ens and Pasquier, 2020), a highly controllable transformer-based model architecture capable of generating multi-track music. MMM is unlike prior models that primarily focused on single-track outputs treating multi-track content as flat sequences or fixed instrumentation. Users can create multi-track music through a controllable and structured process, generating partial or entire musical MIDI pieces with multiple instruments (drums, bass, melody, chords) at once. They can select bars or tracks to be generated with specific musical constraints such as note density, polyphony range and note duration range. The model also offers global parameters (*temperature, bars per step, tracks per step*) which affect what and how it generates musical content. This flexibility and versatility allow the model to fill in, complete, extend, or harmonize multi-track musical ideas based on the existing musical context. MMM was trained on a GPT-2 transformer architecture (Radford et al., 2019) using MetaMIDI (Ens and Pasquier, 2021), a predecessor of the GigaMIDI dataset (Lee et al., 2025), the largest dataset of multi-track MIDI music. Its latest iteration, the MIDI-GPT (Pasquier et al., 2025), further improves performance and adds support for note velocity and micro-timing.

Apollo (Tchemeube et al., 2019) serves as an interactive environment for generating symbolic musical phrases through corpus-based style imitation, enabling composers to explore and emulate musical styles through small data and model crafting (Abuzurairq and Pasquier, 2024). Its workflow, based on Interactive Machine Learning (IML) (Fails and Olsen Jr, 2003), offers model-agnosticity: the system can support any other model for training and generation. Apollo mainly interfaces the MusicVAE model (Roberts et al., 2018) and a Constraint Problem Solver (CSP) model built in house. The MusicVAE model (Roberts et al., 2018) is a recurrent variational autoencoder (VAE) designed for modeling and generating symbolic music sequences, particularly multi-measure melodic and polyphonic phrases with fixed schema (3 to 4 tracks). The system focuses on learning a latent space that supports smooth interpolation, style transfer, and structured sequence generation. It allows users

²Apollo’s project page: <https://metacreation.net/projects/apollo>

³Calliope’s project page: <https://metacreation.net/projects/calliope>

⁴Musical Instrument Digital Interface: a standard computer protocol for communicating symbolic music data.

to create melodies or interpolate between two melodies, producing smooth variations or transitions. It can handle longer-term musical structure than many earlier models and in practice, is used to generate new musical ideas, variations and style blends. The model was trained on large symbolic music datasets with melodies, drum patterns and multi-instrumental pieces encoded in the NoteSequence format. The MusicVAE significantly outperforms standard flat VAE architectures in producing coherent musical phrases over extended time spans (Roberts et al., 2018).

3 Methodologies

In developing Apollo and Calliope, we employed a Reflective Design (Sengers et al., 2005) approach in the context of methodologies which integrate principles from design science research (DSR) and research through design (RtD) (Gaver, 2012). Reflective Design is a methodology for designing technology that incorporates critical reflection throughout the design process. *Reflection* is defined as "referring to critical reflection, or bringing unconscious aspects of experience to conscious awareness, thereby making them available for conscious choice" (Sengers et al., 2005). The goal is not just to create functional systems, but to actively surface and question our underlying assumptions. Reflection is used to highlight and critique the values and practices embedded in the technology, its design and its use. In the case of this paper, it is about bringing awareness to blind spots in the structure of CAC research with regards to tacit knowledge useful for designing and building better CAC systems. We argue that CAC is inherently a multidisciplinary research practice that merges computer science, software engineering and interaction design. Therefore, implicit engineering and design research activities, questions and solutions, which shape the systems we publish, should equally be considered and explicitly discussed to help progress the broader field of CAC. Sengers et al. argues that "*reflection itself should be a core technology design outcome for HCI*" (Sengers et al., 2005). The methodology draws inspirations from prior design approaches: participatory design, value-sensitive design, critical design, ludic design, critical technical practice and reflection-in-action.

DSR (Peppers et al., 2007) focuses on creating and evaluating artifacts that address specific problems, emphasizing the iterative development and systematic evaluation of functional prototypes. Hevner et al.'s framework for design science (Hevner et al., 2004, 2010) in information systems (IS) research outlines a structured approach to artifact creation and evaluation, which has been instrumental in guiding our methodology. Concurrently, RtD (Zimmerman et al., 2007) involves using the design process as a means of inquiry where the act of designing becomes a method for generating knowledge. Then, building on seminal works in Technical Practice Research (TPR) (Sengers et al., 2005) and Critical Technical Practice (CTP) (Agre, 2014), Pelinski et al. specify TPR use for the New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME) research community. TPR is originally a method narrowed from practice research (Pelinski et al., 2024). The latter refers to research endeavors where *practice* is the predominant method for conducting the research work. Practice research is characterized by its reflective approach where research insights emerge through practice itself, articulated by the proxy of documentation, most effectively *reflective writing*. The 'technical' in TPR addresses *technical contexts* or environments where practice typically refers to science and engineering oriented disciplines, i.e., programming, electronic design and digital fabrication. Focusing broadly on reflections rather than critiques, TPR contribute highlights to challenges and nascent opportunities for NIME research (Pelinski et al., 2024). In our work, TPR allows us to capture learnings from the engineering and design practices of building Calliope and Apollo.

RtD involves addressing 'wicked questions', DSR demands a 'structured approach' while TPR takes place within the development process. Yet despite these apparent contradictions, the co-existence of DSR, RtD and TPR in software engineering, interface and interaction design offers a robust framework for supporting CAC research. This also represents an element of contribution in a field where work on new CAC systems is often published without explicit considerations for methodological grounding. In our work, TPR informs *how* systems are built and refined, while RtD frames *why* and *what* is being explored through the system and its use. We draw respectively on TPR (Pelinski et al., 2024) to surface reflections on the development of CAC system discussing technical challenges, and RtD (Gaver, 2012) to frame our inquiry into human-AI interaction through iterative system design. RtD was used early in Apollo research to understand user affordances for designing an interface that supports the IML process for music composition. Conversely, DSR structures the research process of systematically building and evaluating the CAC systems with composers, addressing constructs such as usability, user experience (i.e., authorship, control) and acceptance: this is the case for Calliope

which we evaluated against these constructs with 59 novice composers (Tchemeube et al., 2025). The DSR framework provides a rigorous engineering-centric research methodology that complements RtD and TPR by reinforcing the validity of constructing and evaluating functional CAC systems not just as creative tools of design, but as systematic research artifacts; in particular with regards to analyzing usability and other HCI trade-offs (e.g., interface complexity, AI model controls, user feedback loops, user workflows). Combining these methodologies allows us to produce CAC systems that are both practically useful and theoretically informative.

Finally, the development of both Calliope and Apollo spanned a multi-year period (2019–2024), involving varied contributions from a small multidisciplinary team of a designer, engineers and scientists. The first author was the lead contributor and carried an hybrid role of engineer-designer, responsible for both software engineering and interaction design across all development phases. The term engineer-designer is thus used deliberately to describe the dual responsibilities embodied within TPR and RtD settings, and to highlight the situated, hybrid nature of technical and design decision-making in AI-based CAC system development.

4 Calliope Reflections

4.1 Design Iterations

Calliope has undergone several design iterations from 2022 to 2024, captured by the annotated portfolio (Figure 1). The portfolio’s artefacts highlight research explorations on layout designs for enabling effective MMM-based computer-assisted workflows for multi-track MIDI composition. The first major iteration of the Calliope design, 0.9.5 (Aug 2022), provides a design layout which includes Pianoroll visualizers for each MIDI track of the viewed MIDI file and optimizes for the generative workflow (Figure 3). That means making the “Generate” button, the key user goal of the workflow, more prominently visible on the app (on the middle right) while the control features converge to it (from left to right of the screen). We also explore the horizontal layout of UI items as shown in the “Calliope 0.10 Layout Iteration and Mockupt Test (Jul 2022)” (Figure 1); in particular, the position of the MIDI files’ table and the position for the generate button and its global control parameters.

Calliope 0.10 (Feb 2023) (Figure 1) attempts to make a better use of the available UI space, in particular maximizing the visibility of the piano rolls to support comfortable reading and long and track-heavy MIDI files while minimizing horizontal scrolling to read MIDI notes. It introduces the MIDIVis data visualization tool for exploring generated alternatives. We also shift to a default dark theme to increase contrast and the sense of immersion typical of multimedia applications. Finally, inspired from a Northeastern design study’s feedback, we investigate further mockup concepts and design tests for Calliope 0.11 (Figure 1) that improve readability by emphasizing clear separation among UI items, adjusting the contrast via color palette, and further maximizing the main two UI zones: the piano roll tracks for bar selection (MIDI View Editor), and the “Generate” button with its associated controls. “Calliope 0.11 - Dark Annotated (Apr 2024)” (Figure 1) shows the latest version with the name for each UI section.

The iterative development process also underscores the importance of collaborative design, involving contributions from Northeastern University’s Master CS students under the supervision of their professor Mirjana Ppra (March 2023), in partnership with us at the Metacreation Lab. This collaboration featured think-aloud interviews with professional musicians who tested Calliope by importing MIDI projects exported from their preferred DAWs and engaging with its AI-assisted workflow. Ethics approval (*ID #30000223*) was obtained (for both studies) from the SFU’s Research Ethics Board to conduct this study. The system’s iterative design was refined through user feedback from think-aloud sessions of two professional music producers (one male from North America and one female from Europe) which highlighted the need for intuitive interfaces and responsive features (Figure 2). Warm-up phases and tutorials were instrumental in helping users acclimatize to the system, ensuring they could effectively utilize its capabilities. These efforts demonstrate the value of participatory design methodologies in developing tools that help meet the practical needs of end users.

4.2 Creativity-Support Processes in CAC

Guilford’s theory of creativity (Guilford, 1950, 1956; Lubart, 2001) first posited dual phases of divergent and convergent thinking. It involves generating a wide range of ideas (divergence) before

Figure 2: Calliope's UI Proposal from a Design Research study with Northeastern's AI-HCI Students (2023)

Figure 3: Calliope's CAC Workflow for Batch Generation

Figure 4: Calliope’s MIDI File Visualizer : Per Channel Number, Instrument and MIDI Notes

refining and selecting those that best align with the user’s creative intent (convergence) (Sowden et al., 2019). In the context of Calliope, to support composer’s creativity, this process is mirrored in our design: 1) batch generation enables the user to specify the number of candidates to be generated for each model request and 2) the ranking of generated candidates with respect to style similarity allow the user to distinguish between the output and make further decisions in the creative music process. Thus, the MMM model handle the creation of plausible musical ideas in batch (generation phase), then users evaluate the generated musical alternatives (selection phase) to shape the next request towards a final output. The generative phase in Calliope is well described in Figure 3 where generations are conditioned on specific music data and user-defined constraints; MMM produces valuable and contextually appropriate musical outputs. In the selection phase (convergence), a set of challenges is introduced. When working with large batches of generated outputs, users need tools for evaluation, filtering, and selection to navigate the creative space effectively. This involves comparing ideas, mixing elements, and evolving promising candidates into refined musical pieces that meet the user’s artistic vision.

To support this process, Calliope places a significant emphasis on providing data visualizations. These visual tools (Figure 7) are designed to aid the evaluation process and allow users to navigate and visually compare generated ideas against their initial request. By addressing both the generative and curative aspects of the creative process, Calliope demonstrates how AI can not only produce ideas but also integrate seamlessly into the iterative process of refinement and selection, supporting composers in achieving their creative goals. An in-app onboarding process for navigating the interface and quickly generating music was implemented to guide the user the first time the app is opened.

4.3 Multi-track MIDI Piano Rolls

One of the fundamental challenges in Calliope’s development was building a *functional and intuitive MIDI visualizer for the browser* (Figure 4). As of 2020, online MIDI visualizers were sparse, often outdated, and not designed with modern AI integration or advanced multimedia applications in mind. Creating a visualizer compatible with both AI-heavy computation programs (e.g., Python backends) and real-time multimedia requirements (e.g., music playback synchronized with visual tracking and responsive user interaction) posed significant engineering challenges, many of which remain relevant today. We adopted Google Magenta’s piano roll visualizer object (Magenta, 2018) (Figure 5), built on `Tone.js` (Mann, 2014), a popular Javascript library for audio playback and synthesis. While this solution provided a strong starting point, it introduced several dependencies and engineering constraints. A key issue was the need to convert MIDI files into Magenta’s `NoteSequence` format, a proprietary data structure used by the library. This conversion introduced computational overhead and led to the coexistence of multiple data formats for MIDI encoding within Calliope, complicating the architecture and workflow.

Another significant challenge was in technically adapting Magenta’s piano roll to represent multitrack MIDI compositions effectively (Figure 6). The Magenta library’s piano roll was originally designed

Figure 5: Magenta’s Piano Roll - Hello World Code Example (A Polyphonic Canvas) (Dinculescu, 2019)

Figure 6: Magenta Library’s canvases (piano rolls) in Calliope

for single-channel visualizations, common in piano-based compositions or simple MIDI files. Even when dealing with multichannel MIDI, the library’s default behavior merged all channels into a single roll, limiting its utility for more complex, multi-instrument arrangements. In comparison, digital audio workstations (DAWs) like FL Studio (Line, 1997) or Ableton Live typically represent MIDI data, channel by channel, displaying each instrument or track separately. This granular approach allows composers to focus on individual elements of a piece but is less suitable for Calliope’s use case, where simultaneous visualization of multiple channels is crucial for navigating generative music workflows.

To address this, Calliope implemented a custom solution by instantiating multiple Magenta’s piano roll visualizer objects (Magenta, 2018), (Figure 6), each representing a single MIDI channel. This enabled users to view and interact with all channels concurrently, facilitating a more holistic understanding of the composition. However, this approach came with architectural trade-offs, such as increased computational resource demands and the complexity of managing synchronized interactions across multiple visualizers referencing tracks from the same MIDI file. In addition to visual challenges, Calliope faced limitations with MIDI streaming due to inadequate support in web standards. The W3C’s Web MIDI API (W3C, 2012b) provides basic MIDI handling capabilities, but its adoption and feature set remain limited. Instead, most web-based music applications rely on the Web Audio API (W3C, 2012a), which, while powerful, is not optimized for the kind of real-time MIDI streaming and manipulation required in advanced MIDI-based CAC systems.

Figure 7: MIDIVis Project implemented in Calliope – Tick-by-Tick View (Left): each block is a MIDI file (i.e., 0_1356_t_100.mid), each blue line is a MIDI track (4 tracks in total per MIDI file), the color intensity matches the note density, red lines indicates MIDI note differences or variations between the MIDI files. – t-SNE View (Right): each point is a MIDI file. Hovering on one displays the file name at the top of the graph. The projection and distance between the points (MIDI files) are with respect to the selected musical property, in this case, "Number_of_Pitches", the number of unique pitches in each file (from the jSymbolic library).

Despite these challenges, the development of Calliope’s visualizers underscores the need for innovation at the intersection of AI, music, and web technologies. It highlights the importance of designing intuitive interfaces that balance user accessibility with the technical constraints of real-time multimedia applications. These lessons are invaluable for advancing browser-based AI music tools and fostering more seamless interactions between users and generative music systems.

4.4 Visual Approaches to Evaluating Generated Content

Challenges emerged when ensuring these visualizations are intuitive, actionable, and aligned with user workflows. For example, users needed to assess both the aesthetic qualities of the outputs and their technical coherence with the original project, requiring multidimensional visualization techniques to represent relationships between outputs and user constraints. On the evaluation side, similarity ranking (Ens and Pasquier, 2019), visualized through re-ordering of "variations to the original" from closest to furthest, is employed to compare generated MIDI files based on their musical style. To enhance this process, we developed the MIDIVis project (Figure 7), which incorporates two primary visualizers:

- Tick-by-Tick Diff Visualization: This tool highlights differences between MIDI files at the note level.
- t-SNE Clustering Visualization: Using the t-SNE algorithm (Van der Maaten and Hinton, 2008) and the jSymbolic musical property extractor (Mckay and Fujinaga, 2006), this visualization represents MIDI files as vectors projected on 2D graph. Files are clustered based on similarity, and users can filter the view by specific musical properties, such as pitch classes, drum rhythms, and more. To experiment with this approach, we explored among others t-SNE-based data representation for our collection of music corpora (Figure 8).

These visualizations demonstrate the potential to enhance the usability of CAC systems, particularly for curating and navigating large batch of generated MIDI files. It also helps avoid listening fatigue.

Figure 8: t-SNE Visualization of Calliope's Music Corpora (Testing)

Figure 9: Calliope's Table View of generated MIDI Files

4.5 Organizing Batch-Generated MIDI Files

With Calliope's ability to generate MIDI content in batches, a significant challenge arose: how to manage, navigate, and organize the growing repository of generated material effectively. In the web application, generated MIDI files are saved and displayed in a singular visual list (Figure 9). However, the iterative workflow — where users continuously generate and refine ideas by building upon previous outputs — highlighted two critical user experience (UX) needs (Figure 10): 1) *Recognizing Vertical Relationships*: The ability to identify and group generated MIDI files belonging to the same batch, so from the same user request, 2) *Tracking Horizontal Dependencies*: The ability to identify and track dependencies between generated MIDI files that link one batch request to the next.

Figure 10: Dependency graphs of user generative actions. We see the source MIDI file originating each new batch.

To address these challenges, we explored a few visualization approaches. A potential solution was a tree-based visualization, similar to GitHub’s representation of commit histories, where each batch of ideas branches from a parent request. This could allow users to trace generative dependencies visually. Ultimately, we adopted a 2D visualization approach inspired by projects like the Audio Visualizer, which facilitated intuitive navigation of MIDI files. This approach presented generated files in a spatial layout, making relationships between generations more readable. However, the challenges of managing dependencies and displaying iterative progress remain open issues, pointing to future work in data visualization research for CAC workflows. It hints at pathways for future work that integrates data-driven UX design into music composition workflows, addressing challenges such as dependency tracking, batch organization, and iterative refinement.

4.6 In-Place Editing as a Paradigm

Another potential design approach involves rethinking generative workflows as in-place editing processes. Drawing inspiration from Generative AI applications in other domains, such as image inpainting and speech editing, this approach (Figure 11) would enable users to replace sections of existing material with generated alternatives, maintaining continuity within the composition. For example, in speech editing tools, visual cues highlight editable regions, and hovering over these regions reveals suggested alternatives. This concept could extend to music composition by allowing generated MIDI alternatives to appear as interactive overlays or contextual suggestions (e.g., akin to Microsoft Word’s “word correction” feature). Hovering over a section of the composition could display a drop-down list of batch-generated alternatives. However, while promising, this approach introduces complexities around batch organization and selection, suggesting it as an area for future exploration at the intersection of CAC, AI, and HCI.

Figure 11: In-Place Editing (Mockup) for a 4-track MIDI file. Generations are updated directly on the highlighted MIDI regions. Hovering on a MIDI region displays available alternative generations (that constitute the batch) for that region. User can move across generated batches (currently viewing batch 2).

5 Apollo Reflections

5.1 Model-Agnostic Architecture

Apollo is an original example of the integration of dynamic parametric interfaces for CAC systems, particularly in bridging training and generation workflows (Figure 12). Its interface (Figure 13) empowers users to engage with model training and generation, offering the flexibility to experiment and adjust key settings for each phase. By employing dynamic parametric interfaces, the system facilitates the seamless integration of new ML algorithms. Parameter descriptors and standardized train/generate Python API implementations simplify this process, enabling researchers and artists to experiment with various models without requiring extensive technical intervention. The CAC system was in part conceived to allow to compare various models by hosting them in the same interface, a useful objective for both artists and researchers. This focus on accessibility democratizes the use of advanced AI algorithms in music composition, making them available to users with diverse skill levels. By removing the need for programming expertise, Apollo fosters inclusivity and empowers a broader range of artists to explore innovative AI-driven workflows. This design ethos aligns with the broader goals of CAC research to make creative tools more accessible and versatile.

5.2 Translating Technical ML Jargon

One of the challenges faced during Apollo’s development was ensuring that users could navigate both the technical jargon of AI and the domain-specific terminology of music composition. Model parameters such as the learning rate in MusicVAE configurations, for example, can have a substantial impact on the trained model and thus, on the quality and variability of generated outputs. Yet, the subtle differences between values like “1e-5” and “1e-4” may not be immediately intuitive to users without prior experience in ML. This highlights the critical need for clear documentation, tutorials, and in-system educational tools to help users grasp what the algorithms are, and how these parameters influence the creative process. Bridging this gap required designing an interface that could cater to users with varying levels of expertise. For instance, musicians using Apollo may not be familiar with terms like “learning rate”, “epoch” or “latent space”, while AI researchers may lack familiarity with musical concepts like harmonic progressions or stylistic idioms. Apollo addresses this by

Figure 12: Apollo’s CAC Workflow (Tchemeube et al., 2019)

incorporating contextual explanations with tooltips to educate users and help them appropriate an understanding of the ML jargon for their composition needs.

5.3 Front-End Local Training of Music Models

Another key aspect of Apollo’s design is its implementation of front-end local training of models 13. The system focuses on algorithms optimized for quick training on small datasets or fine-tuning pre-trained models within reasonable timeframes. This allows users to iteratively experiment with different corpus selections and parameter configurations without excessive delays, and without giving their data to the cloud. However, selecting a song or dataset from the corpus to guide training introduces another layer of complexity. Users must understand how their choices influence the learning process, as the stylistic or structural characteristics of the chosen pieces can shape the resulting generative outputs. This is another space for opportunities to assist non-technical users and artists in making informed decisions for training their models.

Apollo’s design exemplifies the importance of user-centricity as opposed to mass-media generation approaches in CAC systems, where accessibility and transparency are as crucial as technical sophistication. By enabling intuitive interactions with complex AI algorithms and fostering a deeper understanding of their mechanics, Apollo empowers musicians and researchers to bridge gaps between interactive machine learning (IML) and music composition. The focus on user education, interface design, and system reliability makes Apollo a model for integrating IML (Fails and Olsen Jr, 2003) into the domain of generative music technologies.

6 Takeaways: From Code to Interaction

Modern CAC systems rely on technical infrastructures to ensure the level of usability and responsiveness critical for AI-based music composition experience. Systems like Calliope exemplify positive approaches to these needs with the integration of Python-based backends for algorithmic processing and Node.js for seamless web application management. Unique design features in these systems (i.e., batch generation and ranking) are needed to address creative workflows, balancing functionality with aesthetic considerations, and ensuring the interface is both easy to navigate and visually engaging for the users. Interfaces designed to display generative outputs such as parameterized piano rolls must be intuitive, responsive, and immersive. The multi-track piano roll (Figure 4) used in Calliope provide users with visual feedback on generated content, allowing them to engage in informed creative decision-making. These visualizers include features like zoomable timelines, customizable track colors, and interactive controls for adjusting algorithmic parameters.

Figure 13: Apollo’s UI Views (2019): 1) Train (or fine-tune) on a small data corpus, 2) Generate new music based on the trained model, 3) Create and browse a small data corpus, 4) Train with a different model and corpus.

Finally, developing CAC systems introduces creative technical challenges. Managing generative wait times requires optimization strategies such as preloading models or user-friendly loading animations to maintain engagement. Handling generative errors such as incomplete outputs or undesirable artifacts demands robust error-checking mechanisms and transparent feedback systems. Converting model outputs into MIDI and synchronizing them with visualizers or streaming them to DAWs involves intricate application design and resource management. These challenges are compounded when dealing with multitrack data, where dependencies between tracks, and support for diverse instrumentation, brings the full complexity of the manipulating the MIDI protocol in the web. Reporting on such engineering and design challenges and opportunities furthers research progress in the development of CAC systems.

7 Conclusion and Future Work

In summary, we presented the design and development of Apollo and Calliope, two CAC systems that investigate scientific research around musical creativity in composition. Through the methodological integration of design science research (DSR), research through design (RtD), and technical practice re-

search (TPR), we reflected on design and engineering work on both systems, exploring particularities, design iterations, challenges and synergies to uncover novel pathways for CAC research.

The advancements and reflections shared in this paper aim to support researchers and developers in navigating the challenges of building novel, user-engaging CAC systems with ever-more complex AI music algorithms and workflows. Importantly, we orient both new and established researchers in overcoming challenges around crafting CAC systems that are not only technically robust but also effectively engaging for users. By documenting the iterative processes, technical solutions, and user-centered methodologies behind Calliope and Apollo, we contribute valuable insights into the ongoing evolution of CAC research.

As the field progresses, fostering more synergies between design, engineering, and user interaction is crucial to unlock new creative possibilities and democratize access to CAC tools. We advocate for more of this type of work to be done to enrich research conversations around the design and engineering of CAC systems.

8 Ethical Statement

The availability of CAC systems, Apollo and Calliope, and of the MMM model is limited to research and noncommercial use. Similarly, music data used to train the MMM model and other models (i.e., in the Apollo application) were utilized under the Fair Use policy for research and private study outlined in the Canadian Copyright Act, allowing the limited use of copyright-protected material without the risk of infringement and without having to seek the permission of copyright owners. It is intended to provide a balance between the rights of creators and the rights of users. This practice is acceptable in the case of academic research, but not for commercial use. Furthermore, OpenAI’s ChatGPT-4 was used to polish the writing of this manuscript. The presented ideas and contributions, as well as their prior writings, remain the original work of the authors.

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